

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.5
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914571
 UDC: 338.43, 339.1, 331.1
 JEL: Q13, Q20, D4

AGRI-FOOD MARKET AS AN INSTITUTION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC INTERACTION

АГРОПРОДОВОЛЬЧИЙ РИНОК ЯК ІНСТИТУТ РОЗВИТКУ СОЦІАЛЬНО-ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ВЗАЄМОДІЇ

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Received 10.01.2024

Левкіна Р.В., Уразгільдієв С.А. Агропродовольчий ринок як інститут розвитку соціально-економічної взаємодії. Науково-методична стаття.

Метою статті є обґрунтування теоретико-методичних засад формування і функціонування агропродовольчого ринку як інституту розвитку соціально-економічної взаємодії, що базується на експлейнарному базисі даного поняття як економічної та управлінської категорії. Критичний аналіз наявних теорій взаємодії дозволив виявити їх спільні характеристики і визначити результат практичної реалізації з точки зору соціально-економічної взаємодії у підприємстві. У якості методологічної основи соціально-економічної взаємодії визначено соціальну відповідальність, яка становить базис стратегії сталого розвитку і означає відповідальне ставлення до природи, ресурсів, готової продукції, працівників, споживачів тощо. Розроблена модель агропродовольчого ринку як інституту розвитку соціально-економічної взаємодії у контексті її внутрішньої і зовнішньої складової. Формалізований підхід до теорій міжособових стосунків дозволив розглядати їх у контексті реалізації соціально-економічної взаємодії у підприємстві і зробити висновок про потенційні можливості часткового поширення на рівень функціонування галузевих ринків.

Ключові слова: агропродовольчий ринок, інститут, соціально-економічна взаємодія, механізм взаємодії, суб'єкти підприємництва

Levkina R.V., Uraghildiaiev S.A. Agri-Food Market as an Institution for the Development of Socio-Economic Interaction. Scientific and methodical article.

The aim of the article is to substantiate the theoretical and methodological foundations of formation and functioning of the agri-food market as an institution for the development of socio-economic interaction, based on the explicative basis of this concept as an economic and managerial category. A critical analysis of the existing interaction theories allowed to identify their common characteristics and determine the result of practical implementation in terms of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship. As a methodological basis for socio-economic interaction, the author defines social responsibility, which is the basis of a sustainable development strategy and means a responsible attitude to nature, resources, finished products, employees, consumers, etc. The article develops a model of the agri-food market as an institution for the development of socio-economic interaction in the context of its internal and external components. The formalized approach to the theories of interpersonal relations allowed to consider them in the context of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship and to conclude that they can be partially extended to the level of functioning of sectoral markets.

Keywords: agri-food market, institution, socio-economic interaction, mechanism of interaction, business entities

The issues of socio-economic interaction are extremely relevant today, as they actually form mechanisms that allow joint efforts to solve problems that cannot be solved by business entities of any industry, non-governmental organizations or government authorities. Only through sustainable cooperation can social entrepreneurial projects, community reconstruction programs, and the launch of socially important and non-profit goods be implemented. Therefore, the topic of the publication is relevant not only at the stage of economic crisis and martial law, it creates a theoretical and methodological basis for the formation of innovative mechanisms for the implementation of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship at any time. Given the conditions of uncertainty and risk in which domestic business entities currently find themselves, which are complicated by the need to operate in the de-occupied territories or in the combat zone, they do almost nothing to solve social problems in local communities. Among such problems on the front pages are those that ensure the life and health of people, hence the problems of food supply, which occurs through the development and functioning of the agri-food market, which is now an axiom and actually represents an institution of socio-economic interaction. The use of this paradigm and further research in the context of defining indicators, criteria, indicators for assessing the level of socio-economic interaction with the simultaneous formulation of the conceptual and categorical apparatus will make it possible to move on to the analysis of the state of socio-economic interaction in sectoral entrepreneurship.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Issues related to the functioning and development of the agri-food market are constantly in the focus of research. Theoretical and practical aspects of the

formation of market relations in the period of reforming the agrarian sector of the economy have been studied: V.Y. Ambrosov, P.T. Sabluk [1], P.I. Haidutskyi [1, 2], Y. Lupenko [3], O.V. Lebedenko [4], as well as the problems of its further development, infrastructure development and introduction of effective mechanisms of market regulation: P.R. Putsenteilo [5], O.H. Shpykuliak [6], O.V. Shubravskya [7] and others. The list of scientific works devoted to various aspects of institutional development of the agri-food market, which are based on the theory of institutionalism and institutions, first formulated by R. Coase [8], D.C. North (Douglass Cecil North) [9].

The experience of social entrepreneurship development came to Ukraine from other countries that currently have a high level of economic development and proves the high efficiency of agricultural social entrepreneurship in terms of solving economic and social problems in a complex. This confirms the relevance of scientific research on the development of market relations on the basis of sustainability and inclusion and their feasibility.

In the context of globalization of economic relations and, above all, agri-food production, not only are the established international relations of the countries of the world and socio-economic contacts of various actors changing, but also social problems arise at the macro- and micro-levels, confrontations and conflicts between market actors are observed where they should not be and where there are common interests. Thus, the issues of forming mechanisms of socio-economic interaction between business structures and other market participants in the context of the worsening economic crisis and further uncertainty, social and economic restrictions (COVID-19 pandemic, local and regional military conflicts, etc.) are becoming more relevant.

Traditionally, scientific research has been limited to issues of economic interaction, which, in a sense, is logical, since economic relations are primary, while social relations are secondary and depend on the effectiveness of the former, as well as on the action of many other factors. The problems of interaction of business entities are paid attention to by such scholars as: N.M. Bogdan [10], L.S. Lisovska [11], G.V. Ortina [12], V.Y. Pazdriy [13], I.P. Tymechno [14], R.V. Feshchur [15, 16], L.G. Shamayeva [17], E.V. Shevchuk [18], and others. These publications are systematic in nature, the authors try to study the category of "interaction" and "economic interaction" using different approaches. Thus, E.V. Shevchuk considers the concept of "interaction" to be an economic and managerial category based on the research of S.V. Mochernyi [19] and others, studies the epistemological field and determines its explicative basis. L.S. Lisovska considers interaction from two perspectives: as a system and as a process, each of which, in our opinion, is correct from a particular point of view.

It should be noted that, according to [11], economic interaction as a system should contain the following components: a common goal, a single result, joint actions, common motivation, a common understanding

of the value of joint actions and the result. Instead, the components of economic interaction as a process are as follows: system elements (subjects of interaction, their contacts and physical movement); joint actions (relationships, information links, mutual influence) and, directly, as a result of mutual understanding, interaction. We fully agree with this definition and support the author's scientific position. Drawing attention to the practical side of using these approaches, we note that the latter approach, where the primary place as elements of the system is occupied by the subjects of interaction, has a higher level of practical significance and allows us to move into the plane of relations between market participants. It is they (the subjects of interaction) who determine and influence joint actions, form the potential for mutual understanding and the result of mutual understanding - interaction [11]. Interesting is the definition of N.O. Yevtushenko, according to which the interaction of business entities is a universal form of relationship between enterprises that carry out "constant social and psychological interconnection of structural elements of different levels on the management system in order to provide a mechanism for organizational and economic development in the long term" [20]. This confirms the inseparability and interdependence of economic interaction and social issues.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Firstly, it should be noted that the authors of the article already have certain research results that are directly or indirectly related to this topic and published in domestic and foreign publications [21-25]. Thus, in [21], the authors presented the developed organizational and economic mechanism for the sustainable development of agricultural enterprises in the vegetable market and formulated a conclusion about the socio-economic interaction between agricultural business entities and other entities at the level of realization of their interests in the market environment. Publications [22-25] are a further development of this scientific idea, they constitute a methodological and methodological basis for further research, which, in combination with the achievements of other scientists [5-7, 11, 18, 19], allow to improve the provisions of the theory and practice of market relations as an institution of socio-economic interaction in agrarian entrepreneurship.

However, despite the existing list of publications based on the results of scientific research, this issue requires further elaboration and development in terms of harmonizing the interests of the subjects of interaction in the system of market relations as a relevant institution.

The aim of the article to substantiate the theoretical and methodological foundations for the formation and functioning of the agri-food market as an institution for the development of socio-economic interaction, based on the explicit basis of this concept as an economic and managerial category. To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set: defining the categorical and conceptual apparatus of institutionalism; generalizing the characteristics of the agri-food market

as an institutional structure; analyzing the concepts of "interaction", "socio-economic interaction" in terms of interaction theories and concepts of a socially responsible enterprise; developing a model of the agri-food market as an institution of socio-economic interaction; formalizing theories of interpersonal relations in the context of implementing socio-economic interaction in enterprises.

The main part

In the current conditions, the domestic agri-food market, which is part of the global market, has shown remarkable resilience to the challenges of the military invasion of Ukraine and post-COVID recovery. The study of its main indicators, problems and development directions is an important tool in the system of measures to increase the competitiveness of not only agri-food products, but also the country's international competitiveness and socio-economic development. The growth of global demand for food resources is justified by the limited agricultural land resources and the growth rate of the world's population, which, according to FAO, has the potential to grow to 9.0 milliards in 2050. The agri-food market is the main source of food raw materials, which is the basis for the production of food and non-food products. On the other hand, the development of the agri-food market contributes to the opening of new business entities in the agricultural and processing industries. According to V.A. Mamchur, the agrarian market is an effective institution that «allows to integrate vertical, horizontal and other ties of enterprises, institutions and other market agents» in the process of production, marketing, processing of agricultural products according to certain rules of relations [26]. P.T. Sabluk directly points out that the agrarian market should be understood as the sphere of interaction between market participants to ensure the production and movement of agricultural products, goods, technologies, means of production, scientific and technical products, etc. [27].

There are certain differences in the concepts of «institute» and «institution». In the first case, it is an institutional structure, that is, an economic system, mechanism, instrument created by the state, society, and business entities. Instead, an institution is stable social and market rules that determine a specific direction of interaction, development of market institutions and create conditions for cooperation. Thus, the agri-food market is an institution of relations: economic, social, sectoral, cooperative, etc. The main task of the institution is to manage production, sales, processing, storage and transportation, which is a set of different but interconnected markets, including sectoral, specialized, etc.

Thus, V.A. Mamchur even systematizes the hierarchical levels of the agricultural market, pointing to their features as a single institutional structure and proposes a structural model of its development. According to this model, the market is influenced by agricultural producers and, through the terms of supply

and retail trade, influences consumers. The formalization of the approach is obvious, as well as the apparent lack of links between the components of the agricultural market. Thus, we believe that the first hierarchical level should be the resource support of the agrarian market, and, accordingly, institutions and institutions should belong to each of these levels by definition, since we are talking about systematizing the levels of the agrarian market as a "single institutional structure" [26]. The structural model of the agricultural market also needs to be improved in terms of defining subjects and objects of management, trade infrastructure, etc. But the main thing is that there is no backlash from consumers of products on market infrastructure actors and producers. Thus, we are talking about the interaction in the market between all its actors, direct and indirect regulatory authorities. That is why effective mechanisms for the functioning and development of institutions should be formed to facilitate the expansion and deepening of socio-economic interaction to address a number of relevant issues in society, increase the efficiency and competitiveness of producers, improve social standards of living and provide quality food at reasonable prices.

The analysis of the existing definitions of the concept of "interaction" allowed us to distinguish several approaches: interaction as cooperation, connections, relations, communication, influence, which is quite limited and logically requires the synthesis of these approaches into a single one, which was done in [18]. The work identifies and characterizes the mechanism of interaction, stages of its formation, conditions, forms, motives, strategies, etc., and the epistemological field is represented by theoretical and applied aspects of interaction, including, directly, theories of interaction, the list of which is quite wide. A critical analysis of these theories has revealed certain common characteristics, such as their attraction to psychodiagnostics, interpersonal relations, sociology, etc. (Table 1).

When formulating the results of this study, we did not address the issues of responsibility of business entities for the results of their own activities. The formalization of the approaches did not require the separation of economic, social, and environmental consequences. Instead, their differentiation and specification allows us to plan measures according to each component, taking into account its specifics. And while natural resources cannot react to such activities by expressing dissatisfaction or protest, employees and consumers are simply obliged to do so within the framework of a conceptual approach to the structure of the market as a relevant institution. When defining the concept of "socio-economic interaction", it is necessary to take into account backlash and balancing of interests, as well as the level of intelligence of each subject, his or her professional and social affiliation, education, psychological qualities, attitude to risk and uncertainty, communication skills, etc.

Table 1. Concepts of a socially responsible enterprise

Concept	Characterization concepts	The result of practical implementation of the concept in terms of socio-economic interaction
The concept of binding obligations	Compliance with legislation and moral and ethical standards; Reporting using economic and social indicators.	Development of society as a whole, employees, and the community
The concept of voluntariness	Additional commitments in line with the development strategy of the enterprise, community, and employees	Development of society as a whole, employees, and the community
The concept of stakeholders	Implementation of the principle of understanding responsibility towards stakeholders	Creating the image of a socially responsible enterprise, building a brand, balancing the goals and requirements of stakeholders, and increasing the efficiency of the enterprise
The concept of corporate accountability	Create a system of reporting to the public on non-financial activities and stakeholder engagement	Formation of a positive image and brand of the company due to the openness of data about the company
The concept of productivity	At the stage of sustainable development, the company reaches the highest level of labor productivity	Shaping the image of a sustainable development enterprise
The concept of indicativeness	Introducing a system of balanced economic and social performance indicators	Building the company's image as a reliable and responsible partner
The theory of synergistic impact	Alignment of social and economic performance indicators	The correlation between social responsibility and financial results indicates synergy in the company
Theory of social action	Social actions (holistically rational, value-rational, affective, and traditional) are closely linked to economic processes in the market for goods (services).	Maintaining the interconnection of the social and economic components allows us to identify the rationalization of an action as a direct social action and achieve business efficiency through the achievement of economic interests

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Thus, we are talking about social responsibility, which is at the heart of the sustainable development strategy and is interconnected with the mechanism of social and economic interaction. Social responsibility means a responsible attitude to the environment, employees, resources and finished products. R.V. Feshchur et al. in their study of the essence of the methodological basis of socio-economic interaction have gone the furthest and consider such interaction between business entities and the environment, internal and external environment at work [15, 16].

The conclusion about corporate social responsibility as a methodological basis of socio-economic interaction was made by them on the basis of processing a wide range of different concepts of an enterprise as a socially responsible one. Thus, socio-economic interaction is schematically presented as a set of three components: the internal environment of the enterprise, the environment (ecosystem) and the external environment (stakeholders), which influence each other. Instead, we are trying to study socio-economic interaction on the example of market relations, where most of the common concepts of the functioning of a socially responsible enterprise are valid.

We have developed a model of the agri-food market as an institution of socio-economic interaction, which is presented in Fig. 1.

In Figure 1, the following abbreviations are used:

ISEI – internal socio-economic interaction;

IEME – internal economic mechanism of the enterprise;

ISP – internal social policy;

SED – socio-economic development;

QMS – quality management system;

IAAMS – information and analytical activity management system;

BMMS – business model management system;

EMS – environmental management system;

ERMS – external relations management system.

It should be noted that the institution of socio-economic interaction successfully combines its internal and external components. The internal component, namely ISEI is a set of types of relations between employees, management personnel, departments or within business processes, as noted by M.S. Tatar. According to [28], the scheme of realization of socio-economic interaction, its further development requires supplementation and clarification of interaction within business processes. It is interesting and appropriate to assume that each business process has a certain subject composition, intensity of interaction, place and direction of interaction, etc. The external component characterizes the interaction between market participants (producers of products, infrastructure companies and consumers of products). Each of these entities (legal entities) enters into external socio-economic interaction and is characterized by internal interaction, experiencing the influence of the state through the use of direct and indirect methods of regulation.

This ensures the profit of market participants, realization of mutual economic and social interests, creation of conditions for maintaining living standards, public health and ensuring a reasonable level of labor reproduction. Globally, such interaction contributes to

solving the food problem in any of its possible manifestations: providing the population with food in accordance with reasonable consumption standards; production of high-quality (organic) products and food raw materials; and availability of food through the trade infrastructure.

The results of the study would not be complete without analyzing the issues of interpersonal interaction that exist at different levels of market relations and within market entities – legal entities. It should be noted that the reasons and manifestations of such interaction are diverse, but they all fall within the scope of theories of interpersonal relations. Traditionally, the analysis is carried out starting from the basic theories – the theory of behaviorism and the

theory of neo-behaviorism, which means "the science of behavior". They are based on the reflexive response to certain stimuli, which is defined as a "stimulus". The stimulus-response scheme itself is widespread and is used in biology, psychology, sociology, etc. Fig. 2 shows a formalized view of the main theories of interpersonal relations in the context of socio-economic interaction.

In particular, A. Maslow and F. Taylor used the theory of neo-behaviorism for managerial purposes to explain the mechanism of decision-making in business. The introduction of intermediate components between "stimulus" and "reaction" allowed to adapt the theory to practical conditions.

Figure 1. Model of the agri-food market as an institution of socio-economic interaction
 Source: the authors' own elaboration

The addition of variable components (external environment, market conditions, etc.) to the boundary between experience ("stimulus") and human behavior ("reaction") ensured the transition from the theory of neo-behaviorism to explaining the causes of interpersonal interaction and socio-economic interaction in the implementation of business processes.

The theory of exchange characterizes the interaction of entities at the level of costs and returns received, which in a formalized form explains the basic relationship between management personnel and employees (subordinates), and the theory of justice evaluates the interaction by determining the correspondence between the result and the contribution based on the conclusion of the establishment of justice.

Figure 2. Formalization of theories of interpersonal relations in the context of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The latter remains relevant to this day and is of practical importance when assessing the interaction between a manager and a subordinate or interaction between employees, when determining remuneration for work performed, etc. From the point of view of symbolic interactionism, interaction occurs at the level of transmitted information («stimulus») and feedback information ("reaction"). Another interesting theory is the psychoanalytic theory, according to which interaction between people is determined by the subconscious choice of a particular decision. We believe that the founder of this theory, Sigmund Freud, took the first steps towards formulating the principles of behavioral economics and human interaction in a saturated market.

Thus, in Fig. 2, we have presented formal models of interpersonal relations in terms of the most common theories and concluded that they are related to the implementation of socio-economic interaction at the micro level and have the potential to be partially extended to the level of sectoral market functioning and even the macro level.

Conclusions

Thus, in this scientific publication, we substantiate the theoretical and methodological foundations for the formation and functioning of the agri-food market as an institution for the development of socio-economic interaction, based on the explicative basis of this concept as an economic and managerial category.

The study of the categorical and conceptual apparatus of institutionalism has led to the conclusion that the concepts of «institution» and «institution» differ in favor of the former in further use for formulating the main results of the scientific work. Thus, an «institution» should be understood as an institutional structure or economic system, mechanism, instrument created by the State, society, and business entities to realize their own or common interests. The analysis of the definitions of the concept of "interaction" allowed us to distinguish several approaches: interaction as cooperation, connections, relations, communication, influence, which require synthesis and combination of these approaches into a

single one. In any case, when defining the concept of "socio-economic interaction", it is necessary to take into account the feedback and building of balances of interests, as well as the level of intelligence of each subject, his professional and social affiliation, education, psychological qualities, attitude to risk and uncertainty, communication skills, etc.

A critical analysis of the existing theories of interaction has made it possible to identify their common characteristics and determine the result of practical implementation in terms of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship. As a methodological basis for socio-economic interaction, the author defines social responsibility, which is the basis of a sustainable development strategy and means a responsible attitude to nature, resources, finished products, employees, consumers, etc. The article develops a model of the agri-food market as an institution for the development

of socio-economic interaction in the context of its internal and external components. The external component represents the interaction between market participants (producers, infrastructure enterprises, consumers of products), and the internal component is the interaction between departments, employees, and interaction at the level of business processes. Thus, ensuring the profit of market participants, realization of mutual economic and social interests, and creation of conditions for ensuring social standards of living are supported by the state at all levels of market functioning. The formalized approach to the theories of interpersonal relations allowed to consider them in the context of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship and to conclude that they can be partially extended to the level of functioning of sectoral markets.

Abstract

The aim of the article is to substantiate the theoretical and methodological foundations of formation and functioning of the agri-food market as an institution for development of socio-economic interaction, based on the explicative basis of this concept as an economic and managerial category. To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set: to define the categorical and conceptual apparatus of institutionalism; to generalize the characteristics of the agri-food market as an institutional structure; to analyze the concepts of «interaction», «socio-economic interaction» in terms of interaction theories and concepts of a socially responsible enterprise; to develop a model of the agri-food market as an institution of socio-economic interaction; to formalize theories of interpersonal relations in the context of the implementation of socio-economic interaction in enterprises. As a result of the study of the categorical and conceptual apparatus of institutionalism, the authors conclude that it is advisable to use the concept of «institution» as an institutional structure or economic system in determining socio-economic interaction in the agro-industrial market. The analysis of the definitions of «interaction» and «socio-economic interaction» allowed the author to identify several existing approaches (interaction as cooperation, connections, relations, communication, influence), the synthesis of which gives the optimal result.

A critical analysis of the existing theories of interaction has made it possible to identify their common characteristics and determine the result of practical implementation in terms of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship. As a methodological basis for socio-economic interaction, the author defines social responsibility, which is the basis of a sustainable development strategy and means a responsible attitude to nature, resources, finished products, employees, consumers, etc. The article develops a model of the agri-food market as an institution for the development of socio-economic interaction in the context of its internal and external components. The external component represents the interaction between market participants (producers, infrastructure enterprises, consumers of products), and the internal component is the interaction between departments, employees, and interaction at the level of business processes. Thus, ensuring the profit of market participants, realization of mutual economic and social interests, and creation of conditions for ensuring social standards of living are supported by the state at all levels of market functioning.

The formalized approach to the theories of interpersonal relations allowed us to consider them in the context of socio-economic interaction in entrepreneurship and to conclude that they can be partially extended to the level of functioning of sectoral markets.

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Посилання на статтю:

Levkina R.V. Agri-Food Market as an Institution for the Development of Socio-Economic Interaction / R.V. Levkina, S.A. Uraghildiaiev // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2024. – № 1 (71). – С. 40-49. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/40.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.5. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914571.

Reference a Journal Article:

Levkina R.V. Agri-Food Market as an Institution for the Development of Socio-Economic Interaction / R.V. Levkina, S.A. Uraghildiaiev // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2024. – № 1(71). – P. 40-49. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No1/40.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2024.5. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10914571.

